

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MacEnulty II****FIRST NAME: Earl****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: MSWord for Mac, version 15

The 5 Key Concepts

1. Not citing common knowledge (EUCLID 2019,10)
2. Signal Phrases (EUCLID 2019,10)
3. Academic Style (EUCLID 2019,12)
4. Get to The Thesis (EUCLID 2019,14)
5. Innie or Outie (EUCLID 2019,15)

ACADEMIC WRITING AT EUCLID - AN INTRODUCTION

1) INTRODUCTION

I have always considered myself an above average writer. I have always enjoyed writing of all kinds: letters to the editors, novels, plays, screenplays and – wait for it – writing papers. I always loved seeing words become sentences, sentences become thoughts or images. I understand innately Edward Bulwer-Lytton’s quote, “the pen is mightier than the sword.” I knew at a very early age that words would become central to my life.

Therefore, I very much enjoyed brushing up on some old concepts while learning new things in the coursepack for period 1, written by Professor Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma. There were many new concepts that I learned, but I specifically will touch on the following: citing common knowledge, signal phrases, formal academic writing, thesis statements and the differences between US and UK English.

2) YOU LEARN SOMETHING NEW EVERYDAY

I was blessed to have the same English teacher, Mr. Freeman, for my sophomore and senior years of high school (back in those days, we only went to high for three years ... tongue firmly planted in cheek). Mr. Freeman was a demanding teacher. He graded a lot of papers in my two years with him. In the earlier stages, my papers were covered in red ink. I took them as badges of courage resulting from my battles with the pen on the page; later, they became a calling to write the pristine paper. The dream of the *un*-marked paper was never achieved but the crashing waves of red ink did dribble down to warbling streams by my graduation.

Strangely, I always knew how to write correctly and well, even if I could not tell you why or how I did it. Even today, if you asked me to diagram a sentence, I would struggle the same as I would balancing a chemical equation in Chemistry. As an adult, I have loved learning the intricacies of writing – through apps and online writing games, to even expanding my vocabulary through crossword puzzles (is there anything better than a hot cup of coffee and the Sunday crossword on the front porch?). All that to say, I still knew good writing when I saw or wrote it.

The coursepack was a summary of the well-written response paper and/or formal paper that EUCLID expects. Beginning with organizing, writing and proofing the essay, the coursepack provided a solid reminder of the elements of strong writing. Moving on to plagiarism, a concept with which I am well suited due to my teaching in the public high school, no new ground was covered but it did provide a nice reminder to the subtler nature of what is and is not plagiarism. Included in this section is the proper way to cite, paraphrase and quote any research used in one's essay. Moving on to literature review, the coursepack provided a handy list of different grammar and spelling quandaries, always a helpful reminder.

By far the most engaging and entertaining of the coursepack was the section detailing the differences between US and UK English. Having spent some time abroad in Australia (more on that later), I was already familiar with some of the differences. Still, this was an enlightening section and will play into part of my discussion in this response paper. From there, the coursepack really “gets into the weeds” with the finer points of writing in the Chicago style with the *CMS Crib Sheet*, written by Dr. Abel Scribe. This section was primarily a brush-up on many key concepts but will also provide a handy reference in future classes. Finally, the coursepack concludes with a wonderful and thorough exploration of Latin phrases commonly used in academic writing. This section was particularly illuminating as I knew some things, which obviously suggest that I was taught them, but many I did not know or remember.

a) **To Cite or Not to Cite, that is the Question**

As a twenty-three-year veteran high school teacher, I am very well acquainted with the values of academic honesty and plagiarism. Given the ludicrous amounts of information

available at our fingertips, I am always amazed at how many students still continue to think we “old people” cannot tell when they’ve literally lifted an entire passage – sometimes *entire* papers! – attempting to pass it off as their own. To open a paper at a ninth-grade writing level then suddenly veer with a sharp left to Ph.D. material is as jarring as traveling from paved highway onto backwater, rutted dirt roads. I mean, come on, if you’re going to cheat, make it worthwhile. While the cat is away, the mice will play but, when the cat returns, it is a very foolish mouse that smacks it on the nose.

Despite this, I was pleasantly surprised to learn the rule regarding not having to cite common knowledge. Actually, I did know it *subconsciously*, I just did not know it was identified as such. Who knew? The example identified by our authors regarding the link between smoking and lung cancer was a stellar example. Our authors say this principle best: “The basic rule you can use is that if it is repeated in many different sources that have you read, then you can assume it is common knowledge” (EUCLID 2019, 10). If I were to offer my own illustration of this concept, I would propose the common knowledge that seat-belts save lives. It is very obvious that people who do not do this take their own lives into their hands, backed up research and data. Still, people still smoke knowing the risks; the same goes for drivers not fastening their seatbelts.

I have always been a big believer in something my dad told me: “You learn something new every day.”

b) Signal Phrases

I love this phrasing and the image it invokes. I imagine a railroad crossing with flashing red lights and dropping traffic-bars clanging, “*Achtung!* Pay attention!”

Again, I have always seen this but did not know it had a name. Simply put, it “signals” an upcoming quote and specifically allows for the author’s name to be used. As Professor Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma (2019) emphasize, “Using signal phrases introduces a quotation or paraphrase by using a verb and mentioning the author’s name” (10).

Who knew? ^[1]_[SEP]

c) I Will Not Write Won’t

The idea of formal academic writing was not new to me; however, I did not know that the use of contractions (i.e., won’t, can’t, etc.) is considered *informal* (EUCLID 2019, 12). Such contractions connote a more personal, a.k.a. informal, style that does not suit a formal academic paper. Therefore, from here on out, the use of the word ‘won’t’ is strictly verboten in my formal writing. Further, personal examples will be used *sparingly* in my formal academic writing. The authors further encourage “finding a balance between the informal and formal” (ibid.), an admitted delicate balance which, I fear, might be teetering towards “*too informal*” in this response paper. I expect that I shall be properly chastened should this be the case.

d) Get to the Point!

As you can tell, I like to wrangle with words, play with puns and dance with diphthongs. Sure, having good voice is highly encouraged and, yes, writing with engaging energy and assertive voice is good for strong writing, academic or not. That said, it was a good reminder for me to get to the point, specifically, the all-important (cue music: Dum dum duh!) Thesis Statement.

Lest there be any confusion (and, no, there was definitely no tongue in cheek with that prior statement), I am a huge fan of strong, clear and concise thesis statements. Mr. Freeman taught me that your thesis statement is your road map. Of course, this was back in the day when actual maps were used to plot out a course for your road trip, which was wise for you to plot out or even highlight *before* you were actually behind the wheel. Today, we turn on the car, connect our phone, speak the address of our destination and press “Go” so that idea of a “road map” might be odd to our younger viewers. He would say, “tell me where I’m going.” This expectation is also said quite succinctly by our authors, “[i]f you do not have a thesis, get one” (EUCLID 2019, 14).

This was a good reminder for me to get right to it in my academic writing. Regarding empty filler language, the authors state,

[s]uch remarks add nothing of substance; indeed, they subtract by distracting from the issues at hand. Moreover, they suggest that the writer is unsure what to say, and is looking for a way to fill some space. You do not want to create that suspicion. So just get right to the point (ibid.).

For myself, who is never short of words, I definitely do not want to create that suspicion. I do hope, however, that I am allowed a short preamble before launching off the diving board into the pool of my paper. (Nice alliteration.) I promise, I will keep it short and sweet. Further, our authors stress, “[d]o not make the writing boring and clumsy” (EUCLID 2019, 15). As a striving novelist and playwright, I can assure you that “boring” is the worst sin any writer can make. “Boring” is death to a writer.

e) I Am an Innie

George Bernard Shaw is famous for wryly observing: “England and America are two countries separated by a common language” (notice the “Signal Phrase”). I have always loved this quote. Having lived and taught in Australia for a year, I was well acquainted with the oft funny differences in our common language. I’ll never forget the time I asked a student to “throw their trash in the trash can” and the absolute blank stare I got in return. He then said, “Did you mean the rubbish bin?” Yes, yes, I did. There were a lot of great moments like that. I once told a student that he was “tardy” in arriving to my class. The class howled! “Tardy! What a word.” Needless to say, even when they were not late, students liked to ask if they were tardy.

This section of the coursepack was very illuminating and entertaining at the same time. Most notably, of course, was the definite delineation between the two in terms of where to place the punctuation: before or after the last quotation mark. I could have lived the rest of my life and would have never realized that there was an intentional difference.

Based on this, I am, like my belly-button, definitely an ‘innie.’ (Sorry, that’s probably more information than you wanted.) So much so that Professors Cleenewerck and Dr. Gulma state in all caps:

That said, ALL grammarians that I have encountered have supported the rule that ALL PUNCTUATION GOES INSIDE QUOTATION MARKS IN AMERICAN PRACTICE (EUCLID 2019, 19)

Message received. From henceforth, I will consistently and for-always place my punctuation before the last quotation mark, God Bless the U.S. of A!

Further, I am well acquainted with the various spelling differences in common words (EUCLID 2019, 27-28). Even still, in my teaching discipline, I prefer the UK ‘theatre’ over US ‘theater’ for its classic connection to British theatre. For some reason, ‘theater’ seems bland.

3) CONCLUSION

For this lover of words and the well-written turn of phrase, I enjoyed this brush up on writing. I learned some new things, brought some submerged ideas from the subconscious to the fore and even had a laugh or two remembering the times in Australia with the Queen’s English.

I can definitely see why this is the beginning course for all EUCLID students, a necessary step ensuring a common purpose in our writing and that we are all on the same “web-page” as we move forward through our respective programs. This first period provides a valuable tutorial in personal and academic writing.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.